

ROBOTICS WORKSHOPS 1ST YEAR

[Deliverable 2.1]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this deliverable is to inform on the process of WP2 “Educational Robotics workshops” describing the curricula created and used to deliver Educational Robotics Workshops (henceforth: ERW) and presenting the quantitative data obtained during the ERWs delivery. The report creates a baseline, which will be used for further modification and improvement of the ERW curricula throughout the ER4STEM project lifecycle. Quantitative data in this deliverable is based on the information reported in the workshop information forms, provided by each partner.

1.2 CORRELATION TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

Draft descriptions of the framework, the criteria for selecting good practices and the activity plan template were initially presented in D1.1 Best Practice & Requirements. These elements correlate with D1.2 ER4STEM Framework First Structure and Roadmap 2nd Year and D4.1 First Version of the Activity Plans.

The ERWs process takes under consideration D6.1 Pre-Kit for Evaluation. Likewise, the quantitative data from the ERWs was collected with respect to the Evaluation process based on D6.1 Pre-Kit for Evaluation and was organized following the data structure defined in D8.1 Data Management Plan.

The structure of this report will be used for presenting the data from the ERWs implementation in the second project year in D2.2 Workshop Report 2nd Year.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT

Section 2 Introduction sets the objectives of this document and, likewise presents a brief overview of its content. Section 3 Activity Plan Structure and Process describes the process of the Activity plan development. By and large, Section 4 Process of ERWS Implementation (Delivery) provides details about how the workshops were implemented and logically, Section 5 ER4STEM Workshops Progress Review represents the current status of the workshops, as well as the quantitative indicators for the progress of ERWs implementation. Section 6 Conclusion / Outlook provides a summary of the conclusions and the next steps to follow for the ERWs development and continuous improvement.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 CONCRETIZING THE CONCEPT OF CURRICULUM FOR ER

Work Package 2, among its other goals, is expected to deliver a generic curriculum, functioning as a mediating instrument between the framework (WP1) and the implementation of ERWs. In an attempt to provide a definition for curriculum, we encountered statements declaring that such a definition is extremely difficult to be given. The question of “what a curriculum is”, is in its nature, a matter of profound philosophical discussion, as it yet revolves around the concept of knowledge and notably, of what is of importance to be learned for the individual within the context of the society in which they function [1]. Thus, the answer to this question is has to be in alignment with theories about values, ideas and priorities [ibid]. Under those circumstances, the topic of curriculum for ER further becomes even more complex, if we consider two specific characteristics of ER: a) they are in fact, innovative technology, the integration of which dictates to take into account best practices and common approaches for integrating digital technologies in education; and b) this integration has to take place in formal (school) and non-formal settings (competitions, science centers, conferences etc.)

To solve this problem we started off with the rather simplified definition of curriculum offered by Walker [1] : *A curriculum is a particular way of ordering content and purposes for teaching and learning in schools... offering a common foundation of essential knowledge and skill* [pp.4]. In order to adapt, however, this definition to ER, we need to extend the milieu, so as to include also a non-formal learning setting (like competitions, conferences, camps, etc.). Correspondingly, when discussing curriculum for robotics, we also have to reflect on its nature as a scientific domain: Robotics could be considered a subject matter as well as a domain for contextualized learning of other subject matters, chiefly the STE(A)M related ones. The latter is also related to the approaches for integrating digital technologies in education. Specifically, Wang and Woo [2] identify three levels of ICT integration in the classroom: a) *micro level* where integration of ICT involves a specific lesson, aiming to support student learning in specific concepts b) *meso level*: where integration involves a specific topic and c) *macro level* where integration of ICT happens at the level of a course.

The curriculum we will develop in ER4STEM will cover the meso and macro levels. Specifically, for formal education setting we will focus on the meso level and we will develop a set of learning activities that will be topic-specific and will be mapped to the curriculum of STE(A)M. For non-formal¹ settings ER4STEM will provide a “curriculum” at the macro level, providing a plan for courses focusing on robotics for STEM, which will cover the learning requirements of a contest or a conference.

2.2 THE LANDSCAPE OF CURRICULA FOR ER

¹ The concept of curriculum in non-formal learning settings might seem contradictory in the sense that non-formal learning is not structured in a way that includes a unified curriculum, accreditation and syllabus as it is the case in formal education. However, in the case of Educational Robotics we can define a technology oriented curriculum that can be followed in camps and conferences and/or contests so that the participants gain a set of specific skills and knowledge about robotics.

D1.1 has identified a set of good practices among which there is a reference to curricula developed for ER. The basic characteristics we identified in these curricula are the following:

- They are organized according to the technology they employ (e.g. in Robotics Academy of Carnegie Mellon University there is a curriculum for Lego Mindstorms, VEX IQ Microcontroller, Virtual Brick, etc.);
- They address broad age groups focusing mainly in middle and high school. However, there are also curricula addressing elementary school students (e.g. squeakland);
- Non-formal learning situations like robotics camps are addressed separately from formal learning situations. However, there are cases where preparation for contests is part of the curriculum designed for schools, which is addressed in a separate section;
- The learning activities introduced are connected to standards and formal curricula. Thus it appears that the majority of the curricula address the meso level we described earlier;
- The learning objectives focus on programming and STEM. In many cases learning objectives also include argumentation and language development (important seems to be the construct of design journal). Furthermore, robotics seems to offer various opportunities for practicing 21st century skills and problem solving;
- Teamwork is an important aspect of a robotics curriculum and in some cases it is supported with relevant material. Specifically, Robotics academy of Carnegie Mellon University provides a power point presentation, which identifies the two main courses of work in Robotics (programming and engineering) and distinguishes four roles in a group (Project Manager, Information Specialist, Communications Specialist and Material specialist);
- Few curricula have an explicit pedagogical background. An elaborate example is offered by Tufts University² that developed a curriculum which includes the WeDo platform. Specifically, the curriculum is based upon the concept of constructionism [3] and is developed around the construct of Positive Technological Development. The philosophy of this curriculum is oriented towards positive youth development (student centered – self-actualization orientation [4]) and it consists of six positive behaviors: content creation (i.e. making and programming a robot), creativity, collaboration, communication, community building, choices of conduct (i.e. experimenting with “what if” questions). The Six Cs behaviors are illustrated in figure 1 adopted from [5].

² <http://schools.nyc.gov/NR/rdonlyres/87A27687-1007-41A4-AF8A-D33FAB423C11/0/WeDoThePlaygroundCurricGrades12.pdf>

Figure 1 The Six Cs behaviors. Adapted from Bers (2010)

To sum up, curriculum in ER4STEM is a mediating artifact between the framework WP1 and the implementation of workshops WP2. The curriculum will consist of: a) the theoretical constructs of the framework, b) the activities developed by practitioners (WP4) c) the existing curricula and d) the results of the evaluation of the workshops (WP6).

2.3 METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING A CURRICULUM FOR ER4STEM

Curriculum development is an endeavor with many difficulties and problems. More often than not, curricula are populated with contradicting values, orientations and interests. Problems in curriculum development are often manifested in the gaps between the intended curriculum (the described curriculum), the implemented curriculum (real life in school practice) and the attained curriculum (learner experiences and outcomes) [6]. This problem in many cases is due to the fact the process of curriculum design follows a top down direction, thus there is a rising effort to include teachers in the design and development process.

To overcome this problem, along with the fragmentation in the domain of robotics caused by the different personal pedagogies and technologies in the field (see also [7]) we will follow in ER4STEM a bottom up approach. Specifically, we will create a curriculum starting from the activity plans already created by the practitioners (teachers, company trainers, etc.) in the first year workshops. In years 2 and 3 of the project, we will refine this curriculum based on the evaluation of the workshops and oriented towards unifying the activity plans under an overarching pedagogical approach that takes into

account the affordances and the special characteristics of robotics as a scientific field and as a domain for contextualized STE(A)M learning.

2.4 THE ER4STEM APPROACH

Assuming the general definition of curriculum being the general plan for educational activities, Adams and Adams [8] define a curriculum as everything that goes in the learners' live such as planned and not planned interaction of pupils with educational objectives, instructional content, materials and resources used and materials and resources not used, the sequence of courses, objective, standards and interpersonal relationships.

Following this definition, the ER4STEM project correspondingly presents the ERW curricula in three integrated components:

- (a) Context – the Framework which defines, encompasses and analyses concepts, such as background of the target group, setting (formal, non-formal), sustainability goals of the workshops and criteria for success. Although in any event, this component of the ER4STEM educational curricula could be considered as a prerequisite for an adequate development of the following two components below, it is a paramount that those components are considered not separately but altogether as integral parts of the educational robotics curricula.
- (b) content - the Activity plan that for the most part structures information around core elements of the ERWs such as learning objectives, space, materials (incl. technological tools, manual, handouts, etc.), social orchestration, teaching and learning procedures, and evaluation methods and instruments. Thus content provides information on the goals of the workshop the instruments required to accomplish them (see section 3 Activity Plan Structure and Process; and
- (c) Process – the ERW implementation process, which describes the sequence of activities to initiate, prepare, deliver and complete a workshop, which could be considered as a step by step walkthrough of a successful workshop delivery (See section 4 Process of ERWS Implementation (Delivery)).

These three components of the curriculum are structured and continuously optimized, so that they would provide all relevant stakeholders with a detailed, but yet easily understandable and visually comprehensive information about the technology used, the pedagogical approaches and methods applied, background requirements, criteria for success and more. Within the first four months of the project implementation, the ER4STEM project partners designed draft activity plans that were successfully implemented in practice within the following 6 months (from February 2015 until July 2016). Despite the relevantly short time period, the ER4STEM project partners managed to successfully cover about 30% of the total number of workshop participants planned for the entire project.

Given these points, it should be noted that the framework and the Activity Plan, by the same token, were developed after a set of good practices was identified and further analysed. This required the application of all project partners' previous experience and expertise, together with developed products related to activity plans, involving innovative use of technologies for teaching and learning.

All things considered, the implementation of the activity plans and likewise, the collection of relevant data, required a standardized implementation process as well as a considerable amount of

coordination, so as to ensure that all results could actually be comparable and of a research value. In essence, such process was developed and applied in parallel with the Activity plan during and for the ERWs implementation which is documented in details within the current document in section 4 Process of ERWS Implementation (Delivery).

All ERWs were designed using a standardised structure for the activity plans and moreover, a similar implementation process. Extensive research data, collected through standardized evaluation procedures, including structured questionnaires, observations, drawings and interviews, was obtained and provided for further analysis. Noteworthy, a significant share of this data will be made publically available under the initiative of the European Commission for open access to data.

These elements were documented and diligently applied within the first ten months of the ER4STEM project from October 2015 until July 2016 in 48 ERWs with 1213 both male and female students of age between 5-20 years old in four different countries, namely Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, and Malta.

The workshops covered different robotics platforms such as Arduino, LEGO Mindstorms, Botball Link Controller, Dash and Dot, Thymio, and LEGO We Do.

The unique experience obtained by the continuous feedback received by all relevant stakeholders (ERW implementation teams, schools, teachers, contributors, etc.) will undoubtedly be applied in the further development and the continuous improvement of the project activities within the remaining two cycles of ERWs in the second and third project years.

3 ACTIVITY PLAN STRUCTURE AND PROCESS³

This section explains the process of development of the Activity plan structure. While the Activity Plan template was designed under WP4 Pedagogical activities, it was among the most crucial elements of WP2 Workshop curricula. All of the ERWs were designed, delivered and evaluated using a standardized structure of the Activity Plan. Therefore, it is important within this report to describe the process of the development of the Activity plan and its structure, as used by all the partners during the first year of the project implementation. Activity plans and the activity plan template will be further developed during the whole lifecycle of the ER4STEM project. The process of the Activity Plan development and its structure are going to serve as a baseline for the further improvement of the future ERWs, as well as to support the design, delivery and evaluation of new ERW, within the remaining two years of project execution. This section of the report will be updated accordingly, in order to ensure that a bidirectional traceability between the Activity Plan structure, ERW delivery process and educational results from ERW is observed.

³ Large part of the content of this section was presented as an article during the Robotics in Education 2016 conference as a part of scientific dissemination activities of ER4STEM project. Nikoleta Yiannoutsou, Sofia Nikitopoulou, Chronis Kynigos, Ivaylo Gueorguiev and Julian Angel Fernandez, "Activity Plan Template: a mediating tool for supporting learning design with robotics" RIE 2016.

3.1 ER FRAMEWORK APPLICATION WITHIN THE WORKSHOPS

The ER4STEM framework is, in its essence, intended to serve as a set of mechanisms, processes and tools (e.g. Activity plans) which would assist teachers, organizers of educational robotics activities as well as educational robotics researchers to design, implement, evaluate and improve the activities. These stakeholders are identified and listed in details in D 1.1. As a result of this, the framework provides processes for pedagogical activities and curriculum design, which could be used by all the three of the above-mentioned stakeholders. Both processes are developed following the same macro-steps: design/adapt, implement, evaluate and improve.

Figure 2 ER robotic framework macro-steps

The first macro-step “design/adapt” is divided into two sub-steps serving as starting points depending on the respective situation. The macro-step “design”, should be followed when there is no previous or not sufficient amount of information available on the activity. Whereas, on the other hand, the macro-step “adapt” should be followed when sufficient information on the activity is available.

In the specific case of pedagogical activities, the following steps were identified for the “design” macro-step:

- *Conceptual design*: helps transform a pedagogical activity into an activity plan, which has been under development within Work Package 4.
- *Developing*: the step where all relevant materials are generated, as opposed to implementing an activity. Possible materials that are developed in this step are handouts, guides and presentations.
- *Adjusting*: is a step in which the activity plan is improved based on the flaws detected during the development.

Each of these steps is divided precisely into defined phases that suggest the proper actions to be taken, in order to achieve a final goal.⁴ The Activity Plan for an individual workshop is explained in details in section 4. Process of ERWS Implementation (Delivery). The curriculum design process will be further developed on the basis of the experience acquired throughout the project, the documented processes, applied by other authors, and last but not least, the use of diverse tools developed or adapted for the project along the implementation phase.

The second macro-step “implement” describes the process that could help during the preparation and implementation phase of the ERW.

Last but not least, the third macro-step - “evaluate and improve” provides information about the specific aspects that should be taken under consideration after the activity has been implemented, in order to serve as a basis for improvement.

The second and third macro-steps are described in details as an actual process in section 4 “Process of ERWS Implementation (Delivery) of this report.

3.2 BACKGROUND

The ERW activities share common elements but they are also very diverse in that they address different aspects of Robotics, such as teaching and learning technology with their success depending on how well these aspects are identified and how well they were addressed. This is partly due to the fact that Robotics as a scientific domain, could be very specific compared to other learning technologies:

- a) Robotics is inherently multidisciplinary, which in terms of designing a learning activity might mean collaboration and immersion into different subject matters;
- b) Robotics is extensively used in settings of formal and non-formal learning and thus involving different stakeholders;
- c) Robotics’ tangible dimensions cause perturbations – especially in formal educational setting - which are closely related to the introduction of innovations in organizations and schools (i.e. from considering social orchestrations to establishing or not, connections with the curriculum, etc.);
- d) Robotics is a concrete example of the constructionist philosophy for teaching and learning [3]; it is relevant to the newest learning practices such as the “maker” movement, “Do It Yourself” and “Do It With Others” communities etc.

All this being said, a need from dissociation from the specific learning activities emerged, creating a possibility for development of a more generic curricula instrument, i.e. an activity plan template, that:

- will be pedagogically grounded on the particular characteristics of robotics as a teaching and learning tool;
- will be adaptable to different learning settings (formal – non-formal);
- will afford generating different examples of learning activities for different types of kits
- will focus on making explicit the implicit aspects of the learning environment and
- will urge designers to think “out of the box” by reflecting on its content.

⁴ Further information regarding all these phases could be found in deliverable 1.2.

Furthermore, the concept of a mediating artefact was adopted to describe a generic learning design instrument that is constructed taking into account:

- a) a specific pedagogical theory; and
- b) the particularities of robotics as technologies.

The activity plan template is an abstraction of what we have identified as essential and transferrable elements of learning with robotics. The activity plan template we present here was used in practice (i.e. designing and implementing workshops) by ER4STEM partners within the first cycle of ERWs. Feedback generated from this process will be used to update the activity plan template so as a) to have a level of abstraction that it will make it adaptable to different settings and b) to have a level of detail that will demonstrate the influence of a specific pedagogical approach and will address the particularities of Robotics.

Gueudet and Trouche [9] focusing mainly on resources and documents designed by teachers (e.g. activity or lesson plans), reveal another dimension of design as they describe it as a tool that not only expresses but also shapes the teacher's personal pedagogies, theories, beliefs, knowledge, reflections and practice. The term they used to describe this process is Documentational Genesis. A core element of this approach is instrumental theory [10] according to which the characteristics of the resources teachers select to use, shape their practice on the one hand (instrumentation) and on the other hand, the teachers' knowledge shapes the use of the resources as teachers appropriate them to fit their personal pedagogies (instrumentalisation). Teacher designs, as a result of the above, intertwined, processes according to Pepin, B. Gueudet, G., & Trouche [11], are evolving or living documents - in the sense that they are continuously renewed, changed and adapted.

Design as an expressive medium for teachers and educators, can also function as an instrument for sharing, communicating, negotiating and expanding ideas within interdisciplinary environments. This property of activity plans is linked to the concept of boundary objects and boundary crossing [12]. The focus here is on the artefact (in our case activity plan) that mediates a co-design process by helping members of different disciplines to gain understanding of each other's perspectives and knowledge. Educational Robotics for STE(A)M is such an interdisciplinary environment which involves an understanding of related but different domains (i.e. Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics) and involves players from industry, academia and organizers of educational activities.

A problem with all these designs, especially when they involve integration of technologies, is that they are driven by a multitude of "personal pedagogies" the restrictions of which result in adapting technologies to existing practices [13]. Conole (ibid) argues that the gap between the potential of digital technologies to support learning and their implementation in practice can be bridged with a "mediating artefact" to support teacher designs. She continues claiming that such a mediating artefact should be structured according to specific pedagogic approaches and should focus on abstracting essential and transferable properties of learning activities that are not context bound. The activity plan template can play the role of the mediating artefact equipping professionals with a structured means to describe, share and shape their practices. This way we can contribute in addressing the problem of fragmentation in the learning activities regarding the use of Educational robotics.

European approaches to STEM education through robotics in one open operational and conceptual framework. It provides a generic design instrument that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics based in theory and practice and in that contributes to the description of effective learning and teaching with robotics.

3.3 PROCESS

Given all of the above, the process, through which the activity plan templates in the project were developed, includes the following steps:

- A first draft of the Activity Plan is created, based on a) identifying and analysing a set of good practices and b) previous work on activity plans that involves innovative use of technologies for teaching and learning.
- The second step requires the use of this first draft for the means of design and implementation of robotics workshops in different educational settings and systems. As a result, the Activity Plans, adapted to the specific objectives as well as to the environment of each workshop, were documented and applied.
- The third step is to improve and further develop the Activity Plans, based on the suggested improvements, and likewise, the experience gained during the ERWs implementation and analysis of the educational results from the workshops.

While the first step, during which we created the first draft of Activity Plans, was a critically important input for the ERWs implementation process, the second and the third steps were fully integrated within the ERW implementation process. They are described in further detail in section 4 Process of ERWS Implementation (Delivery).

During the implementation phase we will collect data that will allow us to evaluate, refine and re-design the activity plan template, so that this would result in a useful and moreover, a pedagogically grounded instrument for designing learning activities.

As of August 2016, the ER4STEM project is within the first cycle of the research, which encompasses the following steps:

- A first draft of the activity plan template, based on a set of previously developed criteria, in order to identify good practices;
- Using the Activity Plan during the ERWs execution during the first cycle of project;
- Refining the Activity Plan in accordance with the experience, gained during the ERWs delivery;

Identifying good practices

The criteria for selecting best practices in the domain of educational robotics were formed through a bottom – up empirical process. Specifically, three researchers from different research teams of the consortium worked independently to select a set of best practices from robotics conferences, competitions, seminars and workshops organized by different organizations. This was the first phase of the selection process, which was not done in a structured way. The second phase included analysis and reflection on phase one. Specifically, the criteria were shaped through:

- a) an analysis of the content of the examples of best practices already selected; and
- b) elaboration of the criteria that researchers had implicitly applied during the selection of the specific best practices.

Next the items that - from the analytic and the reflective process - were identified as a part of what could be considered best practices in the field of educational robotics, were synthesized in one document.

The best practice selection criteria were designed and documented in ER4STEM Deliverable 1.1 Best Practice and Requirements, Section 5 Parameters and Criteria to Identify Good Practices (pp 33 -37) to feed into the activity plans by providing interesting and new ideas for a) concepts, objectives, artefacts b) orchestration c) teaching interventions and learning process d) implementation process and e) evaluation process.

Activity plan template

In this sub-section we discuss the rationale, as well as the main structure of the version of the activity plan template, which represents the generic ERWs curricula. The basic pedagogical theory underlying its design is the concept constructionism, where learning is connected to powerful ideas inherent in constructions with personal meaning for the students. In balance, another aspect underlying our design rationale is the emphasis on the social dimension of the construction process, aiming to cultivate a specific learning attitude growing out of sharing, discussing and negotiating ideas. Another characteristic of this first version of the activity plan is that it is designed to be adaptable to different learning settings (: i.e. formal – non formal).

Thus, the structure of the activity plan template is modular and the intention is to allow “selective exposure” of its elements to different stakeholders (the term selective exposure is borrowed from Blikstein [14] to describe the intentional hiding of some of the template elements, according to the relevant settings or stakeholders).

This version discussed here, is informed by the analysis of the best practices identified and is likewise based on previous work on activity plan templates that aim at the integration of digital technologies in learning [15]. The structure of the Activity plan template addresses the following aspects:

- the description of the scenario with reference to the different domains involved, different types of objectives, duration and necessary material;
- contextual information regarding space and characteristics of the participants;
- social orchestration of the activity (i.e. group or individual work, formation of groups, etc);
- a description of the teaching and learning procedures where the influence of the pedagogical theory is mostly demonstrated;
- expected student constructions;
- description of the sequencing and the focus of activities;
- means of evaluation.

Future work involves refinement of the activity plan template through its use from the ER4STEM partners to create their activity plans and through data collected during the implementation of these activity plans in realistic situations (workshops).

The activity plans initially developed and documented in ER4STEM Deliverable 1.1 Best Practice and Requirements, section 10 ANNEX were further developed, changed or adopted to meet the specific objectives of ERWs, further more they were aligned with the new improved version of the Activity Plan template. The latest version of the Activity plans, developed by the partners as of August 2016 are presented in ER4STEM D4.1 First Version of the Activity Plans.

4 PROCESS OF ERWS IMPLEMENTATION (DELIVERY)

Description of the ERW implementation process aims to provide a clear picture to researchers and teachers on the key steps that were planned and executed within the first year of the project implementation. From a research perspective, the process complements the evaluation data received from the workshops with detailed information on how this data was generated through the ERWs execution. This section of the report represents the process as it was implemented within the first year of the project.

The process description will serve as a baseline for the implementation of the ERWs to be executed during the remaining implementation phases of the project and therefore, for any stakeholders that might be interested in the application of the Activity Plans and similarly, to deliver the ERWs designed and elaborated on within the ER4STEM project.

The ERW process contains four phases, namely Initiation, Preparation, Execution, and Closure that are visually represented within the process scheme as horizontal lanes. The “Prepare ERW delivery” and “Deliver ERW” steps are presented in more details as sub-processes. Each step in the process contains all in all the following properties:

- Entry criteria: criteria which determines when the respective step can be started;
- Inputs: materials, results from other steps and other items that are needed for the proper execution of the corresponding steps;
- Outputs: results, produced during the corresponding steps;
- Exit criteria: criteria, which determines whether the respective step could be considered completed.

4.1 ERW IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS DESCRIPTION

Figure 3 ERW Implementation Process

Process Elements

INITIATION PHASE

AWARE STAKEHOLDERS

Description

A representative/representatives of the Implementation Team takes actions for raising awareness within the target groups about the benefits of integrating ER in the educational process. One or several awareness activities could be performed within this step:

- Distribution of awareness materials via electronic channels such as e-mail, social media, broadcasting;
- Participation in different educational events, such as workshops, conferences, meetings and others;
- Direct meetings with relevant stakeholders;
- Others.

Entry criteria

ERW is designed and prepared

Inputs

- Information and demonstration materials - video, printed materials, multimedia presentations, robots or robotic kits ready for demonstration, analysed data from previously implemented ERWs;
- Representatives from implementation team to be involved in this process are selected and the relevant materials are provided. Target groups are identified, as well as relevant educational events;

Outputs

- A list of relevant stakeholders, who are interested in participating in ERWs;
- General requirements about the implementation of ERW communicated to the interested parties;

Exit criteria

Stakeholders are interested in participating in ERWs

ARE STAKEHOLDERS INTERESTED?

Gates

- NO

- YES

OBTAIN COMMITMENT FROM STAKEHOLDERS

Description

Representatives of the Implementation Team meet decision makers from the organization that will host/ organize the ERWs. Both parties discuss and agree on important aspects of the ERW delivery such as:

- ERW objectives and expected results;
- Space and students info;
- Technical requirements and necessary equipment;
- Content of written consent forms and evaluation procedure.

Entry criteria

The relevant stakeholder is interested to host/ organize an ERW

Inputs

- ERW Activity plan;
- Written consent forms for parents, students and school;
- Information/ demonstration materials and presentations.

Outputs

- Alignment of requirements to the ERW Activity Plan, if needed;
- Alignment of requirements to the Written Consent Forms, if any;
- Official agreement between implementation organization and hosting organization (if necessary);
- List of participants;
- Signed consent forms from parents, students and educational organization;

Exit criteria

Commitment to organize ERWs

ARE STAKEHOLDERS COMMITTED?

Gates

YES but alignment needed

YES

NO

 ALIGN ACTIVITY PLAN

Description

The Implementation Team aligns, if possible and necessary, the ERW Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms to the needs and requirements of the organization that will host the ERW. The needs and requirements may include:

- Specific educational objectives. For instance, objectives might need to be changed because students are already advanced in some of the topics covered by ERW or in case the host organization requests additional topics to be included in the workshop in order to relate them with educational objectives from other fields and subjects;
- Technical constraints derived from the environment. For example, the host organization does not have enough computers available or the computers might be running on a different operation system.
- Organizational requirements. For example, the host organization requires different social orchestration, such as number of students per class, specific criteria for setting up the teams or the available time slots are different than the originally planned time slots in the ERW activity plan.

The Implementation Team changes the original Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms, if possible, in order to satisfy the agreed on requirements provided by the hosting organization. Bi-directional traceability between the changed (aligned) Activity Plan/Written Consent Forms and related activities, materials and artefacts is ensured.

Entry criteria

Changes to the Activity Plan are requested and agreed on

Inputs

- Original ERW Activity Plan;
- Original Written Consent Forms;
- Information Materials;
- Alignment of requirements to the ERW Activity Plan;
- Alignment of requirements to the Written Consent Forms;

Outputs

- Aligned Activity Plan, including clear instruction how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts;
- Aligned written consent forms;
- Aligned information materials.

Exit criteria

Commitment to the Aligned Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms is obtained by all relevant stakeholders

OBTAIN COMMITMENT FROM ERW PARTICIPANTS

Description

The Implementation Team distributes information brochures and Written Consent Forms among the participants (students and their families) and answers any questions and comments that come from the participants or their parents.

Majority of the participants in the ERW sign written consent forms and are familiar with the study and the purpose of data collection and have understanding on how their identity and their data will be protected.

Entry criteria

Obtained commitment to the Activity plan from the ERW organizers/ host

Inputs

- List of participants;
- Written Consent Forms Templates - for organizer/ host, for the participants and their parents;
- Information materials for the workshop, the project and the study;

Outputs

- Signed Written Consent Forms - by hosting organization, by parents and students;
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video or audio recording, agreement to participate in EC open data initiative, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW process and any other information, relevant to the ERW implementation

Exit criteria

All participants and relevant stakeholders provided signed written consent forms. Updated list of participants is developed.

PREPARE FOR ERW DELIVERY

[Go to details of the sub-process](#)

Description

The Implementation Team prepares the workshop delivery

Entry Criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders is obtained and the Activity plan is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts;
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video or audio recording, agreement to participate in EC open data initiative, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW process and any other information, relevant to the ERW implementation
- Evaluation templates;
- Evaluation method.

Outputs

- Materials and artefacts prepared;
- Space and ICT environment ensured;
- Implementation team trained;
- Evaluation materials printed.

Exit Criteria

Outputs are finalized and ready

EXECUTION PHASE

DELIVER ERW

[Go to details of the sub-process](#)

Description

The Implementation team executes the ERW following the specific Activity plan and observation/assessment method, taking into account a target group on which the observation will focus.

Entry Criteria

Workshop prepared

Inputs

- Activity plan
- Materials and artefacts;
- Space and ICT environment;
- Implementation team (tutors) trained;
- Observation/ Assessment methods and tools;
- Tools, equipment and spare parts.

Outputs

- Educational results;
- Collected and processed artefacts and observation/ assessment forms;
- Reflections on ERW and improvement suggestions.

Exit Criteria

ERW finalized

 EVALUATE RESULTS

Description

The implementation team or external expert evaluates achieved educational results according to the educational objectives in the Activity plan and observation/ assessment methodology. Members of the Implementation Team document good practices and issues that were observed and any ideas for improvements that were generated by the relevant stakeholders. Information includes:

- Source (who identified the issue)
- Observation (description of the issue)
- Cause (what caused the issue, if it can be readily identified)
- Suggested improvement (how to solve the problem)

Entry criteria

Delivered workshop

Inputs

- Evaluation method;
- Collected and filed in evaluation documents and educational artefacts;
- Tutor reflections and observations in raw format.
- Improvement suggestions.

Outputs

- Evaluation forms and sheets are filled in by participants and are collected, organized, anonymized and scanned to be further stored in the workshop data base;
- Signed written consent forms are processed and organized into folders;
- Other relevant artefacts of learning, such as code, mind maps, midpoint reflections, etc., are collected;
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed;
- Video or audio interviews with preferably the target group from the study, are performed, transcribed and encrypted;
- Sensitive data, such as participant key, name labels, certificates, photos, videos, etc., is encrypted and stored on an external hard drive;
- Suggestions for improvement and reflections on the workshop are taken into consideration and filed.

Exit criteria

Evaluated results.

4.2 PREPARE FOR ERW DELIVERY SUB-PROCESS

Figure 4 Prepare for ERW delivery sub-process

Process Elements

SET UP SPACE AND ENVIRONMENT

Description

The Implementation team checks the hall/s where the ERW will take place and ensures that the facilities and equipment correspond to the requirements of the ERW defined in the Action plan. When applicable, the Implementation team installs the necessary software on the computers that will be used by the students and tests it to make sure that the software is properly set up.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity plan is aligned as needed

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.

Outputs

- Space and ICT environment
- Access to an appropriate workshop hall guaranteed;
- Workshop desks, power supplies and other special tools/equipment ensured;
- ICT equipment ensured and set up as needed.

Exit criteria

Space and ICT requirements fulfilled.

TRAIN THE IMPLEMENTATION TEAM

Description

All members of the implementation team are trained how to facilitate the ERW. If necessary the team can decide to simulate the workshop and all activities in it. Any specifics of the particular workshop are discussed and actions are planned.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity plan is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts;
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video recording, agreement to participate in open data pilot, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW and any other information relevant to the ERW implementation;
- Evaluation templates;
- Evaluation method and protocol.

Outputs

- Implementation team trained:
 - Scenario;
 - Space and students' information;
 - Social orchestration;
 - Student productions and artefacts of learning;
 - Sequence and description of activities;
 - Evaluation procedures, interviews, reflections, observations and sensitive data.

Exit criteria

Implementation team is capable to execute the workshop

SET UP MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

Description

The implementation team prepare the materials and artefacts for the ERW taking into account any specific requirements for the particular workshop. The activities can include:

- Disassembly/assembly of components of the robotic kits;
- Testing each kit/robot to ensure that it functions properly;
- Modification of students and teachers' guides;
- Others.

Integrity (e.g. right versions) of the materials and artefacts ensured.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity plan is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity plan including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts;

Outputs

- Materials and artefacts prepared
 - Digital artefact
 - Robotic artefact
 - Student's workbook and manual
 - Teacher's instruction book and manual

Exit criteria

Materials and artefacts ready.

PREPARE EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team prints the evaluation forms and ensures equipment for conducting the evaluation during the ERW delivery.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity plan is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Evaluation templates;
- Evaluation method and protocol;
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video recording, agreement to participate in open data pilot, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW and any other information relevant to the ERW implementation.

Outputs

- Evaluation materials printed
 - Draw a scientist form;
 - Pre-questionnaire form;
 - Post-questionnaire form;
 - Observation notes template
 - Reflection sheet form
- Focus group for observation and interviews identified
- Evaluation equipment ready
 - Camera;
 - Audio/ video recorder.

Exit criteria

Evaluation prepared.

4.3 DELIVER ERW SUB-PROCESS

Figure 5 Deliver ERW sub-process

Process Elements

INTRODUCE STUDENT TO THE ERW CONTEXT

Description

The researcher introduces the implementation team, explain the ERW objectives, describe the ERW agenda and provides safety instructions. Explain that video/audio recording equipment will be/is set up in the room and why.

Entry criteria

ERW has started

Inputs

- Aligned activity plan;
- If conducted in a school, informed consent given by the school to carry out the research;
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by parents;
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by students;
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by tutors;
- Signed consent forms stored safely;
- Each student has randomly allocated a student number.

Outputs

- Tutors introduce themselves, the project, the workshop and the study - students are aware of the workshop context and about the study they will take part in;
- Students are introduced to the evaluation methods, which will be applied during the workshops;
- Students understand that they don't have to consent to take part in the evaluation and that this will not result in any negative consequence for them;

- Students know that they can withdraw from the study at any time, without giving any explanation and this will not result in any negative consequence for them
- Students receive and understand safety instructions for participating in the ERW.

Exit criteria

Introduction done

 DRAW A SCIENTIST AND PRE-QUESTIONNAIRE

Description

The implementation team asks students to draw a scientist at work according their notions and to fill in the pre-questionnaire form.

- Draw a scientist at work must be done before the first experience.
- Pre-questionnaire (online or paper copy) collects background information on each student and requires their student number.

Entry criteria

Introduction done and students are aware about the ERW objectives.

Inputs

- Draw a scientist sheet;
- Pre-questionnaire evaluation form;
- Drawing or writing tools;
- Participant numbers stickers or other way to mark participants' work;

Outputs

- Filled in draw a scientist and pre-questionnaire sheets.

Exit criteria

Implementation team collected students' sheets: draw a scientist and pre-questionnaire

 LEAD THE WORKSHOPS SESSIONS

Description

Following the Activity Plan, the implementation team informs students about robotic behaviours, the role of creator-programmer in giving desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. Students create/ assemble robot devices from available parts or consider functionalities/ characteristics of pre-assembled available robotic devices. Students experiment with different values and settings and observe the results during the workshop. Students create programs for controlling the robotic devices. If robotic devices are pre-assembled, the students focus on programming and debugging their own programs. Implementation

team leads the students in researching connections with other scientific domains - mathematics, engineering, biology, chemistry etc.

Entry criteria

Collected filled in draw a scientist and pre-questionnaire sheets

Inputs

- Activity plan;
- Scenarios;
- Tested and assembled/ disassembled robotic kits;
- Installed programs and applications on student computers;
- Provided guides and instructions.

Outputs

- Pictures and videos (if applicable) of the workshop, the artefacts of learning, etc.
- Assembled robot devices;
- Collect the code that each team produced;
- Observation;
- Mid-point reflections conducted in a format suitable to the case;
- Other artefacts - research description, project design description, problem description etc.

Exit criteria

Collected artefacts of students' work

CONTINUOUS OBSERVATION

Description

The implementation team follows assessment method and tools together with blank sheets of questionnaires and interview questions. The observation is implemented during the whole duration of the workshop. The observation can include one or more of the following elements:

- Interview with focus group(s) (implemented by implementation team)
- Peer assessment
- Artefacts of learning (code, robots, plans, reflection, etc)
- Observation notes (filled by the implementation team)
- Reflection sheet (filled by each member of implementation team)

Entry criteria

Designed and developed assessment method and tools

Inputs

- Developed assessment method;
- Printed supporting documents for tutors (observation forms, interview questions, evaluation protocol, etc.);
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students;
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies;
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the observation-related activities;

Outputs

- Target group is observed and interesting moments, phrases, reactions are recorded; if audio or video equipment is used for recording, the equipment is also monitored, and observations are timestamped according to the recording;
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed and stored in the workshop database.
- Observation is accompanied by evaluation forms and other evaluation-related documents and activities;
- If permitted, audio or video recordings are made;
- Conducted short "interviews" with groups, ask questions and if possible, record them to support the evaluation. Each team could write instead a short team reflection on what they have done so far in the format of a blog post. The team's response is discussed within the team (not a sub-set of the team) and is as honest as possible.

Exit criteria

Collected and filed all observation sheets and tools

CONCLUDE THE WORKSHOP

Description

The implementation team gives students feedback about the workshop, gives last minute advice, internet connections for more information and provides important conclusions. The implementation team collects all observation/ assessment sheets and announces the end of the workshop.

Entry criteria

Collected workshop artefacts and observation sheets

Inputs

- Developed assessment method;
- Printed assessment tools and supporting documents for tutors (evaluation forms, draw a scientist sheets, interview questions, evaluation protocol sheets);
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students;
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies;
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the evaluation-related activities;
- Microphone and/or camera;
- Post-Questionnaire sheets printed out;

Outputs

- Evaluation forms and sheets are filled in by participants and are collected by tutors;
- Other relevant artefacts of learning, such as code, mind maps, midpoint reflections, etc., are collected;
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed;
- Video or audio interviews with preferably the target group with minimum 2 students from the study, are performed;

Exit criteria

Artefacts and observation sheets

PERFORM FINAL EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team processes the collected and filed artefacts and observation sheets according to the evaluation protocol. According to the tutor experience and data (last if applicable) the implementation team suggests improvement actions. The Implementation team conducts interviews with the target group of students.

Entry criteria

Artefacts and observation sheets

Inputs

- Developed assessment method;
- Printed assessment tools and supporting documents for tutors (evaluation forms, draw a scientist sheets, interview questions, evaluation protocol sheets);
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students;
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies;
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the evaluation-related activities;
- Camera and/or microphone.

Outputs

Data Collection:

- Observations - video and audio recordings are used to finalise own observation notes.

Preparing Data:

- Session information:
- Draw a scientist:
- Observations.

Artefacts of learning:

- Audio recordings of interviews:
- Workshop Information

- Group information
- Lesson Activity Plans (in English)
- Teaching materials: Handouts, worksheets, presentations, videos or any other material created for the purposes of teaching (in English).
- Paper-based questionnaires;
- Tutor reflections:

Make sure that:

- Student names are blanked out and participant keys are added where necessary;
- Translate; anonymise observation notes;
- Everything is translated in English and anonymised;
- Digitise any non-digital data (scan or take a high-quality photograph);
- Collate each group's work in a separate folder. The folder is labelled with the group's name;
- Transcribe (using template) and translate into English;
- Anonymise Translate free-text responses;
- Input all questionnaire responses in provided evaluation tools;
- Documents are archived and ready to be stored.

Exit criteria

Processed data

5 ER4STEM WORKSHOPS PROGRESS REVIEW

5.1 QUANTITATIVE DATA FROM ER WORKSHOPS PERFORMED BY ER4STEM PARTNERS

During the time period from February 2016 until July 2016, project partners organized 48 ERWs with 1213 participants, which is about 30 % of the planned 4050 students for the whole project implementation phase. It is also important to note that the project partners had to organize and deliver the workshops in a short period of time as the implementation period for the first year of the project started from February, which was the beginning of the second semester in general education schools. The project partners performed more than 60% of the workshops in June 2016 (19 ERWs, 395 students) and in March 2016 (10 ERWs, 270 students). Detailed data about the workshops is presented in Appendix 1 Quantitative data from the ERWs based on the Workshop Information Forms .

The timeline of the ERWs implementation is illustrated in the two figures as follows:

Figure 6 Number of male and female students and number of workshops per month

Figure 7 Cumulative number of male and female students and number of workshops per month

A visual representation of the distribution of ERWs and the respective number of students by project partner could be seen further below. This distribution corresponds to the country in which the respective workshops were implemented. PRIA and TUWien implemented 22 workshops with 501 students in Austria, ESI CEE implemented 13 workshops with 372 students in Bulgaria, UoA implemented 7 workshops with 195 students in Greece and AcrossLimits implemented 6 workshops with 145 students in Malta.

Figure 8 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per project partner

The participants in the workshops were well balanced in terms of gender. Female participants were 46% of the total number of students and male participants were 54% of the total number of students. With a few exceptions, there were no significant deviations between the shares of female and male students based on variables such as implementing partner, robotics kit and programming languages, which yet makes the research rather unbiased in terms of gender in most of its aspects.

Figure 9 Number of male and female participants

About 40% of the workshops had between 20 and 24 participants and 27% of the workshops consisted of between 25 and 29. A number of participants ranging between 20 and 29 students was applicable

for about 67% of the workshops, which closely corresponds to the typical number of students in the normal classes in general education schools.

Figure 10 Distribution of number of ERWs by number of participants per ERW

Most of the students participated in ERW based on Arduino robotics kits (32%)⁵, followed by students that participated in workshops based on LEGO Mindstorms⁶ robotics kits (25%). The remaining workshops used Botball Link Controller (20%), Dash and Dot (12%), Thymio II (10%) and LEGO We Do (5%). With the exception of the ERWs based on Botball Link Controller, the ERWs were generally gender balanced.

⁵ The total sum of % exceed 100% since some of the workshops used more than one robotics kits.

⁶ For the purpose of this report LEGO Mindstorms includes both NXT and EV3 robotics kits and the respective programming languages.

Figure 11 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per robotics kit

Distribution of ERWs based on programming languages correlates with the distribution of the robotics kits that were used for the same ERWs. To demonstrate, 13 of the 14 workshops that applied Arduino-based robotics kits, used Scratch as a programming language and only in one of the Arduino-based workshops, the Arduino was used for programming. Likewise, the LEGO Mindstorms based workshops applied the LEGO Mindstorms programming environment, Botball Link Controller based workshops applied the C programming language. The Dash and Dot based workshops applied Drag and Drop Visuals for their programming sessions, and the Thymio II based workshops incorporated ASEBRA. By the same foot, workshops conducted with the Lego We Do robotics kits applied the native Lego We Do graphic language.

Figure 12 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per programming language

It is important to be noted that most of the workshops were delivered to students with not more than 3 years of difference between the youngest and the oldest participant. Yet, two of workshops reported had, respectively 11 and 7 years of difference between the youngest and oldest participant. (for more information refer to Appendix 1 Quantitative data from the ERWs based on the Workshop Information Forms)

All data in this section is based on the workshop information forms. Some of the indicators could have different values when they are reported in Section 5.2 and in Deliverable 6.3 since the data in those reports is based on the written consent forms and other evaluation artefacts. One should take into account that not all students that had signed written consent forms participated in the workshops and that there were students that had not signed written consent forms but participated in the workshops.

5.2 SUMMARY OF THE EVALUATION PROCESS

Using the pre-kit (D6.1), evaluation data was collected during all of the 48 workshops. Of the 1228 students who had permission to participate in the research, 1133 (92%) completed the pre-workshop questionnaire and 1052 (85%) completed the post-workshop questionnaire. This data is used to gain data on students' experience, attitudes and assumptions. To complement this, 1094 (89%) completed the Draw-a-Scientist task.

To gain an in-depth understanding of the workshops to inform the development of the framework; observer, teacher and student perspectives were recorded through various instruments. In addition to those already mentioned, 39 of the 48 workshops (81%) were observed using a variety of tools including written observation schedules and video. In all but one of the remaining 9 workshops, photographs provided an alternative snapshot record. To understand the workshop from the perspective of the teacher or tutor, reflections were collected from 45 of the 48 workshop tutors (93%). A sample of participants who attended 35 of the workshops took part in a small-group interview after the workshop. This sample represents over 16% of all participants in year 1. Additionally, 83% of students produced personal or team-based reflections on their experiences. The interviews and reflections, supplement the post-workshop questionnaires, observations and artefacts of the learning process, to provide detailed insight into the learner experience during the workshops.

The evaluation of workshops in project year 1 had two aims: 1) to pilot the evaluation kit (pre-kit) and 2) to collect baseline data. Partners involved in using the pre-kit, produced in D6.1 provided additional feedback on the use and usefulness of the evaluation kit which will be used to inform the development of the final evaluation kit to be used in project years 2 and 3. Feedback from partners was collected during and after workshop implementation on the integration of the evaluation into workshops. This shows that while initial data collection at the start of year 1 was hampered by unfamiliarity, over time the evaluation protocol was refined and became a more integrated part of each workshop, thus improving the quality and quantity of data collected. Lessons learned from this process will be incorporated in the refinement of the final evaluation kit, particularly the introduction of questionnaires differentiated by age (D6.2).

Baseline data from project year 1 will be reported in Deliverable 6.3. However, most relevant to this report is that prior to participating in the ER4STEM workshops, less than half of all participants had created a robot or done any programming, with no notable difference between genders as shown in Tables 1 and 2 below.

Table 1 Number of participants that had created a robot before the workshop

Gender	No	Yes	No response	Total
Female	378	134	10	522
Male	338	188	19	545
Total	716	322	29	1067

Table 2 Number of participants that had any previous programming experience

Gender	No	Yes	Blank	Total
Female	294	212	16	512
Male	304	217	24	545
Total	598	429	40	1067

5.3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES RELATED TO ER WORKSHOPS

In light of the need to disseminate and raise awareness about the project, the project goals and activities, including the workshops themselves and the study, partners found the need to present and discuss the ERW activities at various relevant events and direct meetings with school teachers. During those meetings and events, the teachers were provided with general information about the workshops and were offered to participate. One of the project partners, namely AcrossLimits, successfully accomplished this by promoting ERWs in local newspapers and through social media.

To compliment this, the ER4STEM project was also actively disseminated at various meetings with teachers and educators, leading educational organizations, workforce councils etc.

Another channel for the non-scientific dissemination of the project and its goals is the externally organized events (e.g. conferences). An example of this could be ESI CEE's participation at INDEED 2015, the biggest Microsoft Education Conference in Sofia, where the project partner presented the project to an audience of pedagogues in the field of ICT and STEM in general. Another example could be attending Scientix, event known for supporting and promoting a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM professionals, organizations and stakeholders. ER4STEM was promoted also at various meetings with IT companies and similar events, gathering at one place people with possible or known interest in the field of educational robotics.

Most of the partners placed an ER4STEM link on their company/institution's webpages. Some of the partners remained actively engaged in the maintenance process of their websites and managed update them regularly and in a timely manner, publishing important information about the ER4STEM project there. The project is also continuously promoted on Facebook, various newsletters and other social media.

By the same token, interesting information about the ongoing ERW was systematically published in social media an example of which could be the project's Facebook page as well as the pages of the partners, Twitter, You Tube and others. During each workshops the partners always committed to provide extensive information about the project, the core project goals and activities. Correspondingly, some of the partners distributed accompanying materials and stickers branded with the ER4STEM logo. Some of the workshops were video recorded upon participants and their parents' consent and few those videos were approved to go on social media. One o example could be a video of ERW participants building and programming robots – their task was to be able to navigate through a labyrinth. Those videos could be found on YouTube.

5.4 LESSONS LEARNED AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER IMPROVEMENT

This sections informs about the good practices and challenges the project partners had experienced during the implementation of the workshops from process perspective. The information is taken mostly from the tutors' observations as well as from discussion during the regular bi-weekly conference calls between the project partners. This section does not cover in detail the technical aspects of the specific robotics kits and programing environment.

Talking to school teachers and decision makers on teachers' events during the initiation phase proved to be quite useful in order to obtain commitment from all the relevant stakeholders so as to pilot the ERWs implementation. Workshops in the schools, where senior management commitment was obtained, especially at the earliest stages of the communication, were more efficient in terms of efforts needed to plan and execute the respective activities. (ESI CEE)

Working together with school teachers and asking them for feedback (for example, asking for their opinion on how long it will take for the children to take to fill out questionnaires, or whether the students are used to working in groups and building teams, what is the most appropriate time for breaks, etc.) was really helpful during the workshops. Furthermore, teacher involvement and advice were more than valuable within the first phase of the project implementation, as this was what helped a great deal the implementation team to schedule the sessions, and to get to know the children prior to actually meeting them. (PRIA, ESI CEE)

TUWien and ESI CEE had to modify the student number allocation protocol in order to save time and efforts.

What worked really well was to combine different robotics kits in the curricula of the workshops. In one case PRIA started a Botball-workshop with one session with Lego Mindstorms. The students managed to make interrelate concepts between the systems and they seemed to learn the programming language C easily compared to groups using only Botball. ESI CEE incorporated NAO and Finch robots in different parts of the Arduino based workshops to demonstrate more advanced functions of the robots their sensors and other core robotic components and in all of the cases the children were excited by this real life showcase of robotics and were actively participating in the workshop.

What worked well was to adapt the workshops to the interests and the actual learning pace of the children instead to strictly try and follow the workshop plan. (PRIA, ESI CEE) ESI CEE did preliminary interviews with teachers and in some cases tailored the activity plans to the audience. For example, in one workshops, the creativity session based on Tony Buzan's mind-mapping concept was replaced by

more extensive discussions and demonstrations as students were already familiar with it prior to this activity.

In most cases, students loved the fact that they get to work with “real” robots (and computers). The moment where they got to try out the practical implementation of their code and when the robots actually started to move was one of the most exciting moments for both the students and the implementation teams (ESI CEE, PRIA, UoA).

Allocating time for experimentation with the robots was highly appreciated by the students and they were more focused when they were able to try out their own ideas by themselves and see the actual results from their actions (ESI CEE, AcrossLimits).

During the finalizing, the ERWs’ implementation teams had to finalize the evaluation – the separate steps of this project could be seen described in details within point 4.2 of this report, named “Prepare for ERW delivery sub-process”.

This phase took longer time for the implementation teams to complete than initially estimated. As a matter of fact, the execution phase of all of the 48 workshops finished around the end June and the partners needed two months to finalize this workshop closure phase. Based on the partners’ experience gained during this phase of the first year of the project implementation phase, it could be considered as a good practice to be integrated in the ERWs to follow that the closure phase should be completed right after the execution phase of the respective workshops. This proved to be the best working strategies regarding the workshop phase, ensuring effectiveness and efficiency of the process. Not to forget, that the project partners were able, during this pilot year, to identify weaknesses and opportunities for improvement of the evaluation process which would undoubtedly make the process less effort intensive and thus, more efficient and effective as discussed in D6.3 Evaluation and Analysis of 1st Project Year.

6 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK

During the first year of project execution, in a relevantly short period of time the project partners were able to successfully design, implement and evaluate ERWs curricula within 48 workshops with 1213 students in four countries, which established a solid baseline for further research and improvement in the field of educational robotics.

Taking into account that within the first year, the project team was able to teach 30% of the total number of students planned to be covered in the whole project we do not envisage significant risks for the successful completion of WP2 Educational Robotics Workshops.

In the second project year the curricula for the already implemented workshops will be improved, based on the evaluation results and the lessons learned and new workshops will be designed and implemented. The researchers will have the opportunity to work with students and groups that had participated in the ERWs during the first year of project implementation and to observe their attitude towards educational robotics, science and STEM in general, which would be a significant input for this research, as well as the field of educational robotics in general.

7 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

AcrossLimits	AcrossLimits, Malta
EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW	Educational Robotics Workshop
ESI CEE	European Software Institute Center Eastern Europe, Bulgaria
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
PRIA	Practical Robotics Institute Austria, Austria
REA	Research Executive Agency
Relevant Stakeholder	A stakeholder that is involvement in specific ERWs activities.
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TUWien	Vienna University of Technology, Austria
UoA	University of Athens Educational Technology Lab, Greece

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APPENDIX 1 QUANTITATIVE DATA FROM THE ERWS BASED ON THE WORKSHOP INFORMATION FORMS

ERW No	Partner name	Dates from (m/d/y)	Dates to (m/d/y)	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
1	AcrossLimits	5/10/16	5/12/16	2	4	0	10	10	24	10	14	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
2	AcrossLimits	5/11/16	5/13/16	2	4	0	10	10	27	11	16	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
3	AcrossLimits	5/18/16	5/19/16	2	4	0	10	10	20	11	9	2	2	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
4	AcrossLimits	5/26/16	5/30/16	2	4	0	10	10	24	10	14	2	2	12	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
5	AcrossLimits	6/13/16	6/20/16	2	4	0	10	10	26	17	9	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
6	AcrossLimits	6/21/16	6/23/16	2	4	0	8	9	24	16	8	2	2	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
7	ESI CEE	2/16/16	2/23/16	2	2	2	9	10	28	17	11	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
8	ESI CEE	2/25/16	2/25/16	1	2	2	10	10	24	12	12	3	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
9	ESI CEE	2/29/16	2/29/16	1	2	2	12	14	29	12	17	4	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
10	ESI CEE	3/1/16	3/8/16	2	2	2	9	10	27	12	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
11	ESI CEE	3/2/16	3/9/16	2	2	2	8	9	32	22	10	3	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
12	ESI CEE	3/12/16	3/13/16	2	3	1	8	14	17	9	8	4	6	5	Arduino	Scratch
13	ESI CEE	3/15/16	3/22/16	2	2	2	9	10	27	16	11	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
14	ESI CEE	3/16/16	3/23/16	2	2	2	8	9	29	20	9	3	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
15	ESI CEE	3/18/16	3/25/16	2	2	2	9	10	29	14	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch

ERW No	Partner name	Dates from (m/d/y)	Dates to (m/d/y)	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
16	ESI CEE	4/17/16	4/24/16	2	2	2	10	11	25	12	13	3	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
17	ESI CEE	4/26/16	5/3/16	2	1	2	9	10	29	15	14	4	5	7	Arduino	Scratch
18	ESI CEE	4/27/16	5/4/16	2	2	2	9	10	26	18	8	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
19	ESI CEE	5/31/16	5/31/16	1	2	1	5	15	50	21	29	4	6	11	Arduino	Scratch
20	PRIA	2/8/16	2/9/16	2	1	3	13	20	91	76	15	2	9	17	Botball robotic kit	C
21	PRIA	2/16/16	4/12/16	4	1	3	8	10	10	6	4	2	3	4	EV3	EV3
22	PRIA	3/9/16	4/14/16	5	1	1	9	11	21	14	7	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
23	PRIA	3/30/16	3/31/16	2	1	0	12	15	11	8	3	2	3	4	Botball (CBC Controller)	C
24	PRIA	6/1/16	6/3/16	3	1	1	8	11	21	12	9	3	3	7	Lego Mindstorms	Lego Mindstorms
25	PRIA	6/2/16	6/7/16	3	1	0	6	8	23	10	13	10	11	2	LEGO EV3	EV3
26	PRIA	6/5/16	6/8/16	2	1	1	9	11	24	13	11	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
27	PRIA	6/10/16	6/15/16	3	1	0	10	12	21	10	11	10	11	2	LEGO EV3	EV3
28	PRIA	6/13/16	6/23/16	2	1	1	12	14	22	11	11	2	3	9	LEGO Mindstorms and C	LEGO Mindstorms and C
29	PRIA	6/13/16	6/23/16	2	1	1	12	14	22	11	11	2	3	9	Lego Mindstorms and Botball	Lego Mindstorms and C
30	PRIA	6/16/16	6/17/16	2	1	1	9	10	20	9	11	2	3	8	Lego Mindstorms	Lego Mindstorms

ERW No	Partner name	Dates from (m/d/y)	Dates to (m/d/y)	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
31	PRIA	7/20/16	7/20/16	1	2	0	12	15	23	12	11	2	3	8	Botball (Link Controller)	C
32	PRIA	6/21/16	6/21/16	1	2	0	12	14	23	11	12	2	3	10	Botball (Link Controller)	C
33	PRIA	6/22/16	6/22/16	1	1	0	12	14	18	12	6	2	2	9	Botball (Link Controller)	C
34	PRIA	6/27/16	6/28/16	2	1	0	12	13	14	14	0	2	2	7	Botball (Link Controller)	C
35	PRIA	6/28/16	6/29/16	2	1	0	13	14	13	8	5	1	2	7	Botball (Link Controller)	C
36	TUWien	6/1/16	6/1/16	1	1	2	14	15	19	8	11	2	3	8	Thymio II	Native programming language ASEBA - > Text programming
37	TUWien	6/8/16	6/8/16	1	1	2	13	14	20	6	14	2	3	9	Thymio II	Native programming language ASEBA - > Text programming
38	TUWien	6/9/16	6/9/16	1	1	2	13	14	18	12	6	2	3	8	Thymio II	Native programming language ASEBA - > Text programming

ERW No	Partner name	Dates from (m/d/y)	Dates to (m/d/y)	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
39	TUWien	6/15/16	6/15/16	1	1	2	14	16	22	10	12	2	3	10	Thymio II	Native programming language ASEBA -> Text programming
40	TUWien	6/16/16	6/16/16	1	1	2	13	14	21	3	18	2	3	8	Thymio II	Native programming language ASEBA -> Text programming
41	TUWien	6/23/16	6/23/16	1	1	2	14	16	24	7	17	2	3	10	Thymio II	Native programming language ASEBA -> Text programming
42	UoA	3/8/16	4/11/16	6	1	0	14	16	65	32	33	2	4	22	Lego Mindstorms NXT	NXT Programming language (block programming)
43	UoA	3/15/16	3/22/16	2	1	0	13	14	12	6	6	3	3	4	Lego Mindstorms NXT	NXT-G programming software
44	UoA	4/6/16	4/24/16	6	1	0	10	12	34	16	18	3	4	10	LEGO WeDo 2.0	LEGO WeDo graphical language

ERW No	Partner name	Dates from (m/d/y)	Dates to (m/d/y)	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
45	UoA	4/6/16	4/20/16	3	1	0	15	15	25	13	12	4	5	6	LEGO Mindstorms EV3	LEGO Educational Software
46	UoA	4/7/16	7/8/16	2	1	0	16	18	19	12	7	3	4	6	Arduino	Arduino
47	UoA	4/13/16	4/21/16	2	1	0	12	12	25	9	16	2	3	8	LEGO WEDO	LEGO WEDO
48	UoA	4/15/16	4/22/16	2	1	1	12	15	15	14	1	2	3	6	EV3	EV3

